

DETERMINATION OF THE MORPHOLOGY OF A RESERVOIR BASIN BASED ON EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

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ABSTRACT

The article presents studies conducted to determine the current morphology of the basin of the operating alluvial Sardoba reservoir, as well as the coordinates of the relationship between the reservoir volume and water surface area to the water level, established based on the research.

The research was conducted with the aim of determining the current morphology of the Sardoba Reservoir basin following the water overflow that occurred in 2020.

After the overflow event at the Sardoba Reservoir, measures to determine the present water storage capacity of the reservoir basin were carried out based on experimental studies. For this purpose, GNSS STEC SV1 equipment, a Leica Sprinter 250 M digital laser level, ultrasonic Garmin Transducer echo sounders, and SONTEK S5 Doppler profilers were used.

To carry out experimental studies in the reservoir basin, the basin was first divided into 35 cross-sections at intervals of 300 m along its total design length (from the beginning of the basin to the water outlet structure) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Layout of the cross-sections where field investigations were conducted.

All measurement studies carried out in both dry land and water-covered areas were performed using generally accepted geodetic and morphometric standard methods and techniques.

In the dry (non-submerged) part of the basin, measurements were conducted using the GNSS STEC SV1 satellite data receiver and a Leica Sprinter 250 M digital laser level. In the water-covered part of the basin, field investigations were carried out using an ultrasonic Garmin Striker Vivid 7cv Transducer echo sounder.

It is known that there are various methods for calculating the water volume of a reservoir (graphical, analytical, etc.). In practice, graphical, analytical, and grapho-analytical methods are mainly used. To determine the water volume of the Sardoba Reservoir, the grapho-analytical method was applied. For this purpose, elevation contour maps were prepared for several levels from the reservoir bottom up to the normal pool level (NPL) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Contour lines of the reservoir at different water levels.

In the reservoir shown in Figure 2, the areas of the characteristic layers from the free water surface (the highest level) down to the surface bounded by the contour line at the elevation of the reservoir bottom are determined using the triangular method as S_i . The difference between these layers is calculated as h_i , which represents the difference between the elevations of the contour lines.

The water volume between adjacent horizontal levels is determined using the following expression:

$$W = \frac{S_n - S_{n+1}}{2} (h_{n+1} - h_n) \quad (1)$$

The graphical representations of the relationships between the reservoir volume and water surface area and the corresponding water level, as determined from experimental studies, are presented in Figures 3 and 4. The graphs of the results of the experimental studies conducted at the calculated cross-sections are shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 3. Curve of the relationship between reservoir volume and water level determined based on experimental studies.

Figure 4. Curve of the relationship between the reservoir water surface area and water level determined based on experimental studies.

Based on the field investigations conducted, changes in the reservoir storage capacity and water surface area at each water level, relative to the design values, were determined for the current state of the reservoir.

According to the results of the field and experimental studies, at present, at the operating water level of 290 m, the total reservoir water volume is 379.3 million m³ and the water surface area is 28.8 km², while at the dead water level (277 m) the storage capacity is

51.7 million m³ and the water surface area is 3.7 km². Compared to the design values (at the 290 m water level), the total water volume has decreased by 10.7 million m³, and the dead storage volume has decreased by 8.4 million m³.

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